

Moving the National Capital (IKN) from the Strategic Intelligence approach

Sundawan Salya

Lecturer of the State Intelligence Collage, Indonesia

Email: matiindo58@gmail.com

Abstract

The State Capital is the center of government activities that includes administrative institutions as well as an icon of a country. The National Capital relocation project is a significant government agenda, requiring comprehensive and systematic measurements as the basis for government decisions. Strategic intelligence becomes a relevant perspective to measure and map the potential of the plan. Strategic intelligence thinking has a broad spectrum by looking at the importance of multidisciplinary aspects in a policy that includes specific variables ranging from social, political, economic, defense and security, geography, logistics and communication, government and diplomacy. Multidisciplinary parameters and strategic intelligence measurement models can encourage governments to maximize national interests. Therefore, intelligence can provide detailed consideration for the government to make decisions. The data collection method in writing this article was carried out qualitatively by collecting and processing information from the literature and mass media.

Keywords: *The National Capital, Strategic Intelligence, Policy.*

INTRODUCTION

The relocation of the capital city has been a plan that has been echoed by the Government of Indonesia since the second term of President Joko Widodo's administration in 2019. In his statement at the time, President Jokowi stated that Indonesia's new capital city would be built in North Penajam Paser Regency (PPU), East Kalimantan Province.¹ The decision, based on President Jokowi's statement, is the result of a three-year in-depth study by the government. Efforts to move the capital city will go through a long series of processes involving multidisciplinary actors, given the vital role of the capital as the center of government and policy making. Moreover, given the large role of Jakarta which doubles as the center of government as well as the financial center, the issue of moving the capital city also affects Jakarta's role in the future, which involves various stakeholders.

The head of the State Intelligence Agency (BIN), Budi Gunawan, emphasized that the new capital city of the country was carried with an adaptive concept with the times, namely through the concept of a smart city accompanied by green parks for recreation. The head of BIN also emphasized that moving the nation's capital to East Kalimantan would not eliminate the culture and natural 'treasures' in the area. The transfer of IKN only takes up 20% of the forest land used for development, the rest will be maintained and repaired to anticipate the threat of flooding and abrasion. Javanese centrality, or Java-centric, is seen as hampering regional growth and equity in Indonesia. Therefore, the Head of BIN said that the ratification of the IKN Law was a form of seriousness by the government, one of which was to change the stigma that Indonesia was 'only' the island of Java.

On January 17, 2022, the Minister of National Development Planning (PPN) Suharso Monoarfa stated that the new capital city would be named "Nusantara"². The inauguration of the name of the new capital city was carried out simultaneously with the stipulation of the Bill on the State Capital and the establishment of the National Capital Authority which would be the administrator of the government in the city of Nusantara. Previously, the government had also budgeted the cost of moving the capital city of IDR 466 trillion, with 19% of the cost to be met by the state budget³. The relocation of the new capital city is estimated to take five years, starting in 2019. So if it is according to the original schedule, the inauguration of the archipelago as the new capital city will take place in 2024.

If withdrawn, previous studies stated that there were a number of considerations underlying the decision to move the country's capital city from Jakarta to East Kalimantan. First, are environmental factors related to the carrying capacity of Jakarta as a city. As a megapolitan with a population in the city of more than 12 million people and continues to increase,

¹Kate Lyons, "Why Is Indonesia Moving Its Capital City? Everything You Need to Know," The Guardian, August 27, 2019, sec. World news, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/aug/27/why-is-indonesia-moving-its-capital-city-everything-you-need-to-know>.

²Kiki Siregar, "Indonesia Minister Announces Name of New National Capital in Eastern Kalimantan," CNA, January 22, 2022, <https://www.channelnewsasia.com/asia/indonesia-new-capital-name-nusantara-east-kalimantan-2440426>.

³Erwida Maulia, "Jokowi Announces Indonesia's New Capital in East Kalimantan," Nikkei Asia, August 26, 2019, <https://asia.nikkei.com/Politics/Jokowi-announces-Indonesia-s-new-capital-in-East-Kalimantan>.

Jakarta's carrying capacity for its population is increasingly limited.⁴Moreover, Jakarta is facing environmental problems in the form of sea level rise and land subsidence due to excessive groundwater extraction. Not to mention, air pollution in Jakarta is getting more complicated along with the increasing number of residents and private vehicles on the highway. In addition, geographically, Jakarta is known to be a city prone to earthquakes.⁵Jakarta has experienced several earthquakes which can threaten the government and financial sectors at any time. Socially, problems in Jakarta such as inequality, slum settlements, and crime are also crucial aspects that need to be considered⁶. The capital city as the center of government certainly requires a stable and conducive social climate to support the performance of the bureaucracy.

From the considerations above, there is one root cause of the complicated problem from Jakarta which has become a further impetus for moving the nation's capital city, namely its status as a center of government as well as a financial center. It is clear that Jakarta has expanded too far and has experienced a drastic decrease in the carrying capacity of the city. The separation of status between the center of government and finance is expected to be a momentum for improvement for Jakarta and remove the ambiguity of its status so that it only becomes a financial center. Of course, in the future, it is hoped that Jakarta will be more organized in various sectors. This paper attempts to explain the dynamics of moving the nation's capital city with a strategic intelligence approach. This approach uses multispectral analysis to provide an overview of the new capital city, country is mainly related to its prospects, challenges and advantages. It is hoped that this analysis will also be taken into consideration by the relevant policy makers in developing and implementing the role of the country's new capital city in the future. Meanwhile, this paper attempts to answer the formulation of the problem, namely how the strategic intelligence approach views the dynamics of moving the nation's capital in a multi-aspect and multispectral way.

METHOD

To answer the formulation of the problem above, research to examine the perspective of strategic intelligence related to the relocation of the national capital was carried out qualitatively with a literature study. Considering that the issue of moving the national capital is still very actual, primary sources related to this issue are quite limited, so most of the data comes from news and press reports, both printed and electronic. Nevertheless, state documents and journal articles are still sought to be sources for this analysis. In addition, considering the multispectral orientation of the study, analysis of sources from various fields of science becomes the method for reviewing the literature in this research.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Social and Cultural Aspects

As a national strategic project that is quite massive, the relocation of the national capital of course also intersects with social and cultural aspects, especially related to several things. Among them, are the consideration of moving the country's capital city itself, the selection of PPU Regency as the location of the Nusantara City, and how the Nusantara City can later become an inclusive city, friendly to local culture, and able to overcome the gap between local residents and immigrants. The acute social gap that occurs in Jakarta and throughout Indonesia is one of the considerations in this aspect, particularly regarding the paradigm between "the people of Jabodetabek" and "the people outside Jabodetabek"; and "Java" and "outside Java". Furthermore,

The relocation of the country's capital city to Kalimantan Island is intended to reduce the disparity in the focus of social development by the government. Areas outside Java that are in the past, the tendency to lag behind in social development will receive more attention, especially in the eastern part of Indonesia. Moreover, since the era of President Soekarno, the gap in the government's social attention between Java and outside Java has repeatedly created friction and negative perceptions of the government which tends to be Java-centric, even triggering a number of physical rebellions. If it continues, such conditions can certainly threaten the stability and resilience of the Indonesian nation which can latently lead to separatist movements.

In addition, social inequality in Jakarta due to the difficulty of access for middle-low income people to a decent source of livelihood and the high price of basic necessities is a complicated social issue.⁷Poverty associated with crime is a real impact of this social inequality. This of course breaks the focus of the central government, which should focus on administering

⁴"Academic Papers on the Draft Law on the State Capital," Academic Report (Jakarta: Ministry of National Development Planning/Bappenas, March 2020).

⁵"Academic Papers on the Draft Law on the State Capital.", p. 41

⁶Edna Tarigan and Niniek Karmini, "Indonesia's Capital Is Sinking, Polluted and Now Moving," January 27, 2022, <https://thediplomat.com/2022/01/indonesias-capital-is-sinking-polluted-and-now-moving/>.

⁷FISIP UI, "Study of Social Aspects of Moving the National Capital | Faculty of Social and Political Sciences - University of Indonesia," February 27, 2020, <https://fisip.ui.ac.id/kajian-cepat-social-pemindahan-ibu-kota-negara/>.

the state at the central level, into having to take part in dealing with issues that should be prevented and corrected by policy makers at the level of the Special Capital Region. It is hoped that, along with the relocation of the national capital, the DKI Jakarta Regional Government and supporting actors will focus more on taking and implementing effective and ideal policies to address social problems at the regional level and restore Jakarta's inclusiveness as a megapolitan national financial center.⁸

On the other hand, the construction of the capitalThe new state, which has been started since 2019, must involve local communities. In a sense, local communities especially indigenous people are involved in planning, implementing development, and considering supporting infrastructure in the area. As is known, the PPU Regency area is inhabited by multicultural people, especially the Paser Dayak community who have a strong tradition of preserving their cultural heritage.⁹ In addition, there are other ethnic communities, such as Banjar, Kutai, Bugis, and so on who have their own local wisdom.

The involvement of local communities is very important with several crucial objectives, First, so that the new national capital can truly become an inclusive city. As the nation's capital, Nusantara City will later have to reflect the harmonious life of the Indonesian people, maintain social tolerance, and be based on *Bhinneka Tunggal Ika* which is in line with the values of inclusiveness. The new capital city should not exclude local residents, which of course will exacerbate social inequality itself. Second, is the threat of erosion of local culture due to the influx of immigrants in the location of the new capital city of the country. Preservation of local culture must also be considered, considering that local culture is also a nation's wealth and heritage that must be preserved. Besides that, Efforts to preserve local culture can also anticipate the negative reactions of local communities in line with drastic socio-cultural changes that may occur due to the migration of people to the new capital city of the country. To ensure socio-cultural stability, the government also needs to learn from the horizontal conflicts that occurred in Kalimantan in the previous era which resulted in broad community segregation.¹⁰

Political Aspect

The relocation of the nation's capital city to the outer islands of Java has a significant political purpose, namely an effort to represent a central government that is more "Indonesia-centric" and away from the "Java-centric" view in politics. It means, the transfer is a vision so that politics in Indonesia is more evenly represented by all people throughout the region. As is often the case, until now the national political narrative that tends to be Java-centric is still strong enough to resonate in various public spaces, given that political resources—such as constituents and funds are still concentrated in Java or controlled by ethnic Javanese. The lack of representation of residents outside Java can certainly cause jealousy and become a challenge for the unity and resilience of the Indonesian nation.

In addition, based on Mahmud's study of the constitutional aspects of the issue of moving the state capital, it was underlined that the transfer had implications for the implementation of the *trias politica* legislative, executive, and judicial. First, the status of Jakarta as a Special Capital City Region (DKI) based on Law Number 32 of 2004 will certainly change and will experience a decline in status to an ordinary province.¹¹ So, the specifics inherent in accordance with the law will be handed over to the new capital city authority later. Second, the change in this "privileged" status also needs to be considered from the perspective of the local community as a constituent in the new capital city area of the country. In addition to representation, political support from the local community for the change in the status of the capital city is of course also important to consider in order to minimize political tensions that lead to instability.

The last political aspect is related to the establishment of the National Capital Authority (IKN Authority) in accordance with the Law Invite the State Capital with the following analysis. First, the government's decision regarding the appointment of the Head and Deputy Head of the IKN Authority from among development planners is the right decision, considering that they are the ones who are in direct contact with urban issues, including urban planning and urban planning. The political background of the development planning figure is also a strong consideration for the government, considering that this position is a strategic position. Moreover, the project to relocate the national capital is a massive and national-scale project. So far, there are four strong candidates for the Head of the IKN Authority, namely Basuki Tjahaja Purnama, Bambang Brodjonegoro, Abdullah Azwar Anas, and Tumiyana.

Based on a number of sources, job The supervisor is at the same level as the Minister and has broad powers. The Head and Deputy Head of the IKN Authority will later be elected and responsible to the President of the Republic of Indonesia

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ Ajeng Irma Macshury, M Bahri Arifin, and Syamsul Rijal, "PEMALI IN PASER ETHNIC CULTURE IN PASER DISTRICT: A SEMIOTICS OVERVIEW," *Journal of Cultural Sciences*4 (2020).

¹⁰ Virna P Setyorini, "Don't Forget the Socio-Cultural Aspects When Moving the Capital City," *Antara News*, August 1, 2019, <https://www.antaraneews.com/berita/988752/jangan-lupakan-aspect-social-kultur-saat-move-capital-city>.

¹¹ Abd Majid Mahmud, "POLITICAL AND SOCIAL ASPECTS OF MOVING THE COUNTRY'S CAPITAL TO EAST KALIMANTAN," *Journal of Justice*2, no. 2 (November 28, 2020), <https://ejurnal.unikarta.ac.id/index.php/ijj/article/view/795>.

with the consideration of the DPR. These rules are contained in the State Capital Law, starting from Article 5 to Article 9.¹² In addition, the IKN Authority has a number of other characteristics in the field of government, namely having a provincial-level form of government and having its own government regulations which will be completed by the central government within one month.¹³ This relates to aspects of concurrent government affairs carried out by the IKN Authority, namely education, health, protection of local communities, to social affairs.¹⁴ However, the IKN Authority itself does not have a Regional People's Representative Council (DPRD). This means that decisions related to policies in IKN will be planned, implemented, and regulated directly by the Central Government through the IKN Authority as the executor. In addition, in accordance with the State Capital Law, IKN's own income will later be obtained from tax levies carried out by the IKN Authority.

Economic Aspect

The economic aspect is another consideration in the plan to relocate the national capital, especially related to equitable distribution of economic development. A number of academic studies have been conducted to provide support for the economic considerations of moving the capital city with varying results. On the one hand, as reviewed by Katadata, there is optimism regarding the results of equitable distribution of national economic development after the relocation of the national capital with a number of considerations. First, the island of Kalimantan as the location of the new capital city of the country is a potential area for infrastructure development, given the high potential of natural resources being utilized and the construction of new industrial centers in East Kalimantan. Second, based on the Bappenas study, along with the above potential,

On the other hand, other studies are relatively skeptical of the positive economic impact of relocating the nation's capital. INDEF, for example, stated that economic growth due to the relocation of the nation's capital in 2024 is projected not to be as significant as the Bappenas projection given that there is still an economic crisis due to the COVID-19 pandemic that needs to be resolved by the government. This argument is also supported by the status of the new capital city which is projected to only be the center of government and not the economic center, so the potential for increasing economic growth is not too significant. Moreover, it is also projected that it will not be built. INDEF noted that relocating the nation's capital would only increase the province's short-term economic growth (East Kalimantan) by 6.83% and decline to 4.8% in the long term.

However, as has been underlined in the analysis of the political aspect above, the relocation of the national capital also needs to take into account the vision of political representation. This means that the goal of economic equality is also a narrative that supports the vision of political representation, especially regarding the development of regions outside Java. In addition to being related to the politics of representation and equitable development, these efforts also go hand in hand with equal distribution of development carrying capacity, considering that Java Island, which is the location for more than 50% of the population and 60% of national industry in 2020, experienced a decline in the carrying capacity of development. Of course, the vision of economic development that is carried out must be in line with sustainable development, respecting the existence of local communities, and not being the basis for divisions between local communities and immigrants.

Defense and Security Aspects

As the center of government which is the location for the joints of the state apparatus (center of gravity), the position of the national capital is of course very vital. This means that the capital city of the country must be protected and have a good defense. Every country expects that internal and external threats will not approach or even occupy the national capital. Practically, there needs to be a strategic military unit on full alert to protect the capital city, complete with installations and the main tools of an adequate and effective weapon system (defense system). Not only that, the defense-security aspect of the capital is also related to its location as a command center, which means that all military operations are controlled from that location, including building deterrence and deterrence effects against threats.¹⁵

DKI Jakarta, which is currently still the state capital, for example, is protected by a number of strategic military units. On the ground, there is the Jayakarta Regional Military Command (Kodam) located in the city center, supported by other units such as the 1st Infantry Division/Kostrad in Cilodong, Depok and a number of Air Defense Battalions. From the sea, there is the Fleet 1 Command with a number of strategic warships guarding the Jakarta Bay area. In certain situations, for example, when there is a provocation by ships of the People's Republic of China maritime militia in Natuna, the command

¹²Merdeka, "The New Capital of the Archipelago Led by an Official at the Ministerial Level, Elected by the President," merdeka.com, January 18, 2022, <https://www.merdeka.com/events/ibu-kota-baru-nusantara-dipimpin-pejabat-minister-level-elected-by-president.html>.

¹³The detikcom team, "Tito: Head of the IKN Authority at the Ministerial Level, the Government at the Provincial Level," detiknews, February 16, 2022, <https://news.detik.com/berita/d-5945664/tito-head-authorita-ikn-selevel-ministers-government-level-province>.

¹⁴*Ibid.*

¹⁵Makmur Supriyatno, "CONSIDERATIONS FOR MOVING THE COUNTRY CAPITAL FROM DEFENSE GEOGRAPHIC PERSPECTIVE," *Journal of Defense & National Defense* 3, no. 1 (August 7, 2018): 1–24, <https://doi.org/10.33172/jpbh.v3i1.373>.

is also ready to be dispatched. Meanwhile, from the air, there are air bases surrounding the DKI Jakarta area, such as Halim Perdanakusuma and Pondok Cabe which can be used at any time to land and take off fighter aircraft.

Thus, the relocation of the national capital must also be followed by strategic considerations of defense and security. Moreover, geographically, the location of the new capital city is quite close to the Malaysian border when compared to DKI Jakarta, so that the entrance to external threats will be closer. In addition, the country's new capital city is also adjacent to the Indonesian Archipelagic Sea Lane (ALKI) and the Flight Information Region (FIR) of a number of neighboring countries, such as Malaysia, Singapore, the Philippines, and Brunei.¹⁶ These two problems can become the basis for disputes between Indonesia and these neighboring countries which will certainly threaten regional stability. Another threat is the location of the new capital city which is within the range of some of the PRC's ballistic missiles which are strongly suspected to be installed in the South China Sea which also poses a strategic threat to the entire territory of Indonesia.¹⁷

The implementation of strategic defense and the deployment of troops are crucial things that need to be considered by policy makers regarding security aspects in the new capital, especially with the presence of a large number of important actors (VVIP) there from high-ranking state officials to representatives of other countries.¹⁸ Practically, the strategic military command related to securing the national capital will also be transferred.¹⁹ In addition, external threat deterrence units such as anti-missile and anti-ballistic systems, as well as anti-access/area denial (A2/AD) systems are the implementation of a significant and effective defense strategy to defend the country's new capital city. All dimensions of the TNI both land, sea, and air can be integrated to create an adequate defense-security system for the new national capital.

Geographic Aspects and Disaster Management

The development of the new capital city of the country requires careful geographical considerations and includes various factors. Among them are geographic location, accessibility, climate and weather, hydrological factors—related to the presence of waters, to vegetation. For example, it is the new capital city of other countries in the world, such as Brasilia (Brazil), Abuja (Nigeria), and Nyaipyidaw (Myanmar). The cities above were built with the geographical location in mind relatively in the middle, making it easy to reach from all over the country.²⁰ In addition, the lowland location of the capital city allows for better accessibility and reduces the cost of constructing complex road infrastructure. This accessibility is also related to the role of the national capital as a center of gravity that must be protected.

In relation to the previous aspect, namely defense-security, defense geography is another perspective that needs to be considered, along with the importance of accessibility for the deployment of military forces for the defense of the national capital.²¹ The climate of the new capital city is also considered so that it is not too hot, cold, or humid to anticipate extreme weather. Furthermore, another important consideration in choosing the geographical location of the national capital is the disaster aspect related to the geomorphological and geological character, considering that Indonesia itself is a country prone to various natural disasters, ranging from geological, hydrological, and meteorological natural disasters.

The selection of the island of Kalimantan specifically the province of East Kalimantan as the location for the new capital city also took into account a number of geographical aspects with a multi-hazard risk approach. The island of Borneo itself is an area that is geologically inactive, especially in the province of East Kalimantan, where there are no active volcanoes or faults.²² This is a factor in the minimal risk of earthquakes and volcanic eruptions in the location of the country's new capital city, in contrast to DKI Jakarta which is repeatedly rocked by earthquakes with significant strength.²³ In addition, the landscape of the country's new capital city is relatively flat, making it easier for infrastructure development and accessibility from the region to major cities in the vicinity, such as Balikpapan, Samarinda, and Tenggarong. However, the risk of hydrological natural disasters must also be considered so that the vulnerability to floods and landslides can be reduced. Luckily, the area of the new capital city is not too close to the river mouth or the coast with high waves which is a distinct advantage for the country's new capital.²⁴

¹⁶Khoirul Anam, "Duh! There Are Many Defense Threats in the New Capital," CNBC Indonesia, December 28, 2021, <https://www.cnbcindonesia.com/news/20211228171002-4-302753/duh-ternyata-banyak-ancaman-pertahanan-di-ibu-new-city>.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ antarnews.com, "Security Matters in New Capital City Plans," Antara News, October 1, 2021, <https://en.antarnews.com/news/191957/security-matters-in-new-capital-city-plans>.

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

²⁰ Rini Rachmawati et al., "Best Practices of Capital City Relocation in Various Countries: Literature Review," in E3S Web of Conferences, vol. 325, 2021, 07004, <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202132507004>.

²¹ Makmur Supriyatno, "CONSIDERATIONS FOR MOVING THE COUNTRY CAPITAL FROM DEFENSE GEOGRAPHIC PERSPECTIVE," Journal of Defense & State Defense 3, no. 1 (August 7, 2018): 1–24, <https://doi.org/10.33172/jpbh.v3i1.373>.

²² "Environmental Implications of Indonesia's New Planned Capital in East Kalimantan," Policy Brief (Resilience Development Initiative, December 2020).

²³ "Environmental Implications of Indonesia's New Planned Capital in East Kalimantan."

²⁴ Osmar Salih, "Relocating the Capital of Indonesia from a Disaster Perspective," preprint (INA-Rxiv, November 25, 2019), <https://doi.org/10.31227/osf.io/6edng>.

The location of the country's new capital city which is close to the rainforest even though it is advantageous because there is dense vegetation as a climate regulator, also needs to be considered. The development and relocation of the capital city must create the minimum possible environmental impact in order to protect the environmental sustainability of the protected rainforest. Moreover, there is a lot of rare biodiversity that lives in the protected area, especially within a radius of 2,000 square kilometers which is planned to become the spatial area of the new capital city of the country.²⁵ Coordination with stakeholders in the environmental and forestry sectors as well as environmental experts is important to ensure the development and relocation process runs in a sustainable manner. In addition, to ensure that the carbon footprint resulting from human activities can be suppressed, strong regulations need to be enforced so that the country's new capital city is not immediately overrun by residents and disrupts sustainable development efforts in the region.

Aspects of Transportation and Logistics

Still related to geographical aspects, transportation and logistics are strategic aspects so that the implementation of governance and dynamics of the country's new capital city goes well. There are several crucial considerations related to transportation aspects, among them first, as a new city being built, the City of Nusantara needs to be equipped with adequate access to supporting cities in the vicinity, such as Balikpapan, Samarinda, Tenggarong, and Penajam. Moreover, state administration requires efficient supporting facilities, especially transportation, given the many needs that must be met and the provision of facilities in the form of logistics which may have to be distributed from these supporting cities, including to the gates of other regions in Indonesia and the world, namely international ports and airports.

The second consideration is the transportation facilities in the new capital city. Considering the condition of the planned city is not as crowded and congested as DKI Jakarta because it only functions as the center of government, the public transportation network is projected to be simpler and will not be crowded with passengers. However, public transportation still has to prioritize accessibility and user convenience, including punctuality. So, the latest transportation technology such as *slight rail transit* (LRT) can be an alternative to public transportation in the new capital city. In addition, the use of electric vehicle technology also needs to be considered to remove the stigma of the national capital as a "polluted city" as happened in DKI Jakarta. Supporting facilities such as electric vehicle charging stations are crucial facilities that are built.

In other words, the development of transportation and distribution logistics not only considers smoothness and timeliness, but also environmental sustainability and technology. Moreover, the development carries the concept of *smart, green, and integrated* which demands sustainable transport planning. As emphasized by Nurron et al in their study, the nation's capital city no longer shows the image of a crowded, chaotic, and polluted city, but is beautiful, sustainable, and high-tech. This is in accordance with the concept of a forest city, along with the Nusantara City area which is surrounded by protected rain forests that emphasize environmental sustainability and sustainability as the foundation of development.

Infrastructure and Communication Aspects

Still related to the analysis of aspects of transportation and logistics, infrastructure and communication are also related to the smooth transportation of goods, services, and data from and to the new capital city of the country. As the center of government, the smooth flow of information is absolutely necessary in the development of the nation's capital city, so that communication infrastructure becomes a crucial aspect. In addition, the presence of the nation's capital city is also expected to open up investment opportunities in the development of infrastructure and communications in stages in the East Kalimantan region. This is in line with the government's vision stated by the Ministry of National Development Planning/Bappenas in the 2020 National Dialogue on the Transfer of the National Capital, that the IKN area will not become an "enclave" area that is isolated from the surrounding area.²⁶ Instead, IKN is directed to develop the surrounding area. Practically, the development of the national capital will be directed at connecting one region to another with the existing infrastructure.

The government plans to build various infrastructures to facilitate communication. News from the Ministry of Communication and Information (Kemkominfo) stated that a communication network would be built *Borneo Ring* which is planned to start in 2021. Data flows at IKN no longer have to be brought to Jakarta or Singapore first which can reduce internet speed.²⁷ Later, the internet network will be an independent network with several supporting networks. In addition, another thing to consider is the provision of the latest telecommunications network, namely 5G. It is planned that IKN will

²⁵ "Environmental Implications of Indonesia's New Planned Capital in East Kalimantan."

²⁶ PDSI KOMINFO, "Development of the National Capital Involves Local Communities to Develop the Digital Industry Sector and Innovation," Official Website of the Ministry of Communication and Information of the Republic of Indonesia, 2020, http://content/detail/24653/pembinaan-ibu-kota-negara-libatkan-local-community-to-develop-digital-industry-sector-and-innovation/0/article_gpr.

²⁷ PDSI KOMINFO, "Build a Kalimantan Ring for Telecommunications in the New Capital," Official Website of the Indonesian Ministry of Communication and Information, 2022, http://content/detail/21084/bangun-kalimantan-ring-untuk-telekomunikasi-di-ibu-new-city/0/highlight_media.

have a 5G network, but it is not certain when it will be built and operated.²⁸ These networks are expected to be able to change the negative stigma of the Kalimantan region which has been labeled as having "inadequate communication network infrastructure". Moreover, the smart city vision promoted by the government in building the country's new capital clearly requires internet network access that is so smooth for various purposes, such as data processing and storage, telecommunications, to artificial intelligence.

On the other hand, the government needs to be aware of security threat factors related to telecommunications, especially cyber security. All related institutions, from the National Cyber and Crypto Agency (BSSN), the State Intelligence Agency (BIN), to the Ministry of Ekominfo as policy makers in the field of cyber security must work together to support the strengthening of cyber security. BSSN data in 2020 noted that Indonesia faced 495 million cyber attacks, some of which targeted strategic targets, such as government websites, vital national communication systems, and so on.²⁹ Again, cyber security also needs to be seen as a national strategic threat and the status of IKN as the center of government and a symbol of the state needs to be realized to strengthen telecommunications resilience and of course, become a momentum to expand cyber security as a whole throughout Indonesia.

CONCLUSION

From the analysis of the relocation of the nation's capital from the strategic intelligence approach above, there are several things that can be concluded. First, that the analysis of the dynamics of the country's new capital city starting from planning, development, control, to its supervision needs to be carried out in a multi-aspect and multidisciplinary manner, considering the many sectors touched on or influenced by this strategic project. In addition, these efforts are also in line with the collection of intelligence information, which is focused on the potential opportunities, challenges, and obstacles that will be faced in relocating the nation's capital city. So far, these potentials are also very broad in scale and need to be tested with a multidisciplinary approach. Second, this research finds that the process of moving the national capital cannot be done instantly and with the assumption of "one-size fits all" or one solution to all problems. Based on the strategic intelligence perspective analysis, there needs to be further planning regarding strategic problems that must be faced and eliminated as well as opportunities that can be utilized for the national interest. To overcome strategic problems and take advantage of the opportunities that exist in relocating the nation's capital city, there needs to be a synergy between policy stakeholders for maturation of planning and policy implementation. For example, the Ministry of National Development Planning/Bappenas as the policy planner for IKN transfers also needs to involve other ministries and state institutions at the ministerial level such as Lemhannas, BIN. Finally, studies related to the relocation of the capital city are increasingly crucial to be carried out to provide advice, consideration, and policy analysis to the government. This is important so that there are many check and balance actors who can comprehensively contribute to policies that have a national impact. In addition, public political support especially from local communities needs to be integrated into the implementation of this policy. The relocation of the nation's capital city which produces a multi-sectoral impact will certainly affect the lives of local people. The support of the local community is important to maintain the socio-political order, culture, and stability.

REFERENCES

1. Anam, Khoirul. "Ouch! It turns out that there are many defense threats in the new capital." CNBC Indonesia, December 28, 2021. <https://www.cnbcindonesia.com/news/20211228171002-4-302753/duh-ternyata-many-ancaman-pertahanan-di-ibu-kota-baru>.
2. betweennews.com. "Security Matters in New Capital City Plans." Antara News, October 1, 2021. <https://en.antaranews.com/news/191957/security-matters-in-new-capital-city-plans>.
3. Azhar, Hanif, Helmya Fatima, and Isna Tamas. "Preliminary Study of Indonesia Capital City Relocation Based on Disaster Mitigation Principle with Mental Model Approach." E3S Web of Conferences 148 (January 1, 2020): 06002. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202014806002>.
4. State Cyber and Code Agency. "Cyber Attack Recap 2020," 2020. <https://bssn.go.id/rekap-serangan-siber-januari-april-2020/>.
5. Bayu, Dimas Jarot. "Can the relocation of the capital city overcome economic inequality? - Katadata Data Analysis," April 30, 2021. <https://katadata.co.id/ariayudhistira/analysisdata/60893a162c992/capable-pemindahan-ibu-kota-metatasi-ketimpangan-ekonomi>.

²⁸Intan Rakhmayanti Dewi, "Supporting Smart City Implementation in New Capital City, Kominfo Prepares 5G Telecommunication Infrastructure," iNews.ID, January 20, 2022, <https://www.inews.id/techno/telco/support-penerapan-smart-city-in-capital-new-kominfo-prepare-telecommunication-infrastructure-5g>.

²⁹ National Cyber and Crypto Agency, "Cyber Attack Recap 2020," 2020, <https://bssn.go.id/rekap-serangan-siber-januari-april-2020/>

6. Bestari, Novina Putri. "When will the country's new capital have 5G? This is what the Minister of Communication and Information said." CNBC Indonesia, January 20, 2022. <https://www.cnbcindonesia.com/tech/20220119184527-37-308831/Kapan-ibu-kota-negara-baru-punya-5g-ini-kata-menkominfo>.
7. Dewi, Intan Rakhmayanti. "Supporting Smart City Implementation in the New Capital City, Kominfo Prepares 5G Telecommunication Infrastructure." iNews.ID, January 20, 2022. <https://www.inews.id/techno/telco/support-penerapan-smart-city-di-ibu-kota-baru-kominfo-prepare-infraktur-telekomunikasi-5g>.
8. "Environmental Implications of Indonesia's New Planned Capital in East Kalimantan." Policy Brief. Resilience Development Initiative, December 2020.
9. Farida, Farida. "Indonesia's Capital City Relocation: A Perspective of Regional Planning." *Journal of Regional Development and Financing Perspectives* 9, no. 3 (August 31, 2021): 221–34. <https://doi.org/10.22437/ppd.v9i3.12013>.
10. FISIP UI. "Study of Social Aspects of Moving the National Capital | Faculty of Social and Political Sciences - University of Indonesia," February 27, 2020. <https://fisip.ui.ac.id/kajian-cepat-social-pemindahan-ibu-kota-negara/>.
11. KOMINFO, PDSI. "Build a Kalimantan Ring for Telecommunications in the New Capital City." Official Website of the Ministry of Communication and Information of the Republic of Indonesia, 2022. http://content/detail/21084/bangun-kalimantan-ring-untuk-telekomunikasi-di-ibu-kota-baru/0/sorotan_media.
12. — — —. "Development of the National Capital Involves Local Communities to Develop the Digital Industry Sector and Innovation." Official Website of the Ministry of Communication and Information of the Republic of Indonesia, 2020. http://content/detail/24653/pembinaan-ibu-city-negara-libatkan-lokal-to-kembangkan-sector-industri-digital-dan-inovasi/0/article_gpr.
13. Laucereno, Sylke Febrina. "Mass Transportation Development in New Capital City Continue?" *detikfinance*, June 23, 2020. <https://finance.detik.com/properti/d-5065429/pembangun-transportasi-massal-di-ibu-kota-baru-continued>.
14. Lyons, Kate. "Why Is Indonesia Moving Its Capital City? Everything You Need to Know." *The Guardian*, August 27, 2019, sec. world news. <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2019/aug/27/why-is-indonesia-moving-its-capital-city-everything-you-need-to-know>.
15. Macshury, Ajeng Irma, M Bahri Arifin, and Syamsul Rijal. "Pemali in Paser Ethnic Culture in Paser District: A Semiotics Overview." *Journal of Cultural Sciences* 4 (2020): 15.
16. Mahmud, Abd Majid. "Political and Social Aspects of Moving the Country's Capital to East Kalimantan." *Journal of Justice* 2, no. 2 (November 28, 2020). <https://ejurnal.unikarta.ac.id/index.php/jlj/article/view/795>.
17. Maulia, Erwida. "Jokowi Announces Indonesia's New Capital in East Kalimantan." *Nikkei Asia*, August 26, 2019. <https://asia.nikkei.com/Politics/Jokowi-announces-Indonesia-s-new-capital-in-East-Kalimantan>.
18. Independent. "The New Capital of the Archipelago Led by an Official at the Ministerial Level, Elected by the President." *merdeka.com*, January 18, 2022. <https://www.merdeka.com/events/ibu-kota-baru-nusantara-dipimpin-pejabat-secepat-menteri-selected-by-ppresid.html>.
19. "Academic Papers on the Draft Law on the National Capital." Academic Reports. Jakarta: Ministry of National Development Planning/Bappenas, March 2020.
20. Daughter, Yollanda. "The Analysis of New Capital City in Indonesia for Sustainable Development Country Goals." Singapore, 2019. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344076105_The_Analysis_of_New_Capital_City_in_Indonesia_for_Sustainable_Development_Country_Goals.
21. Rachmawati, Rini, Eko Haryono, Rizki Ghiffari, Hilary Reinhart, Farah Permatasari, and Amandita Rohmah. "Best Practices of Capital City Relocation in Various Countries: Literature Review." In *E3S Web of Conferences*, 325:07004, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202132507004>.
22. Salim, Wilmar, and Siwage Dharma Negara. "Singapore | 1 October 2019 Shifting the Capital from Jakarta: Reasons and Challenges." *ISEAS Perspective*, no. 2019 (2019): 9. https://www.iseas.edu.sg/images/pdf/ISEAS_Perspective_2019_79.pdf.
23. Saputra. "Indef: Capital Relocation Will Not Contribute Much to Economic Growth | Economy." *Bisnis.com*, April 16, 2021. <https://economy.bisnis.com/read/20210416/9/1382249/indef-pemindahan-ibu-kota-no-akan-kontansi-banyak-ke-percepatan-economy>.
24. Setyorini, Virna P. "Don't Forget the Socio-Cultural Aspects When Moving the Capital City." *Antara News*, August 1, 2019. <https://www.antaraneews.com/berita/988752/jangan-lupakan-aspect-social-kultur-saat-moving-ibu-kota>.
25. Salih, Osmar. "Moving the Capital of the State of Indonesia from a Disaster Perspective." preprints. INA-Rxiv, November 25, 2019. <https://doi.org/10.31227/osf.io/6edng>.
26. Please, Sahat Aditua Fandhitya. "Economic Impacts and Risk of Moving the Country Capital." *Brief Information XI*, no. 16 (August 2019): 6.
27. Siregar, Kiki. "Indonesia Minister Announcements Name of New National Capital in Eastern Kalimantan." *CNA*, January 22, 2022. <https://www.channelnewsasia.com/asia/indonesia-new-capital-name-nusantara-east-kalimantan-2440426>.

28. Supriyatno, Makmur. "Considerations for Moving the Country Capital from Defense Geographic Perspective." *Journal of Defense & State Defense* 3, no. 1 (August 7, 2018): 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.33172/jpbh.v3i1.373>.
29. Tarigan, Edna, and Niniek Karmini. "Indonesia's Capital Is Sinking, Polluted and Now Moving," January 27, 2022. <https://thediplomat.com/2022/01/indonesias-capital-is-sinking-polluted-and-now-moving/>.
30. detikcom team. "Tito: Head of the IKN Authority at the Ministerial Level, the Government at the Provincial Level." *detiknews*, February 16, 2022. <https://news.detik.com/berita/d-5945664/tito-head-otorita-ikn-selevel-menteri-governmental-selevel-province>.
31. Tri Jeniawati, Diani. *Analysis of the Plan to Move the Capital City of Indonesia from Jakarta to East Kalimantan*, 2019.
32. Yanwardhana, Emir. "All-Electricity, New Capital Transportation Made Sophisticated!" *CNBC Indonesia*, May 25, 2021. <https://www.cnbcindonesia.com/news/20210525131828-4-248226/serba-listrik-transportasi-ibu-kota-baru-dibikin-canggih>.